

Sustainable observations for sustainable Arctic environmental forecasting

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The Arctic is very sensitive to climate change, and the widespread consequences of the Arctic amplification of global warming is evident across the whole Arctic, in all domains affecting both natural and human systems. Sea ice is thinning and more mobile, and the length of the summer melt increases, while sea-ice extent is decreasing (Figure 1), which has already led to a fast increase in shipping (pame.is/ourwork/arctic-shipping/current-shipping-projects/arctic-shipping-status-reports/). Permafrost is thawing, releasing unknown quantities of greenhouse gases, causing erosion and infrastructure failures. Vegetation changes and forest fires are more common and widespread. With all changes follow new weather patterns and extremes, and environmental changes that pose new potentials and threats to societal development, to individuals and to the natural environment.

Models for weather, ocean and ice forecasting and for climate projection at increasing resolutions are improving. Forecasting is now coupled across important domains, including sea ice and ocean, while artificial intelligence is revolutionizing environmental forecasting. Climate projections include the carbon cycle, atmospheric chemistry and aerosols. Hence, we now talk about “environmental forecasting” and “Earth system modeling” rather than weather forecasting and climate models. But the need to document, understand and predict change across timescales from hours to decades is urgent and models need observations.

Figure 1 Arctic climate change, with (top) the warming trend and amplification factors (Rantanen et al., 2022, doi: 10.1038/s43247-022-00498-3) and (bottom) annual minimum sea ice extent (www.climate.gov)

Models OK – what about observations?

A foundation for understanding and modeling is observations and observing is an integral part of all environmental forecasting. Long-term monitoring makes it possible to recognize new patterns and models allow understanding of complicated interactions. Improving physically based models relies on process-level understanding that only comes from observations revealing how different

Figure 2 Examples of Arctic observation cover focusing on the Arctic Ocean: (a) International Arctic Buoy program cover for 9 January, 2025, (b) the WMO synoptic weather observation stations north of 65°N, and (c) cover of atmospheric sounding profiles for September & October 2024.

parts of the system interacts. Observations are needed to initialize forecast models, crucial for safety and wellbeing of society and individuals. Artificial intelligence and machine learning requires more observations. Assimilating

observations into models is a corner stone of weather forecasting since decades but has also become an important tool in climate monitoring. Media reports on climate records from e.g. Copernicus (Climate Change Services Services) it is not observations, but model data using assimilated observations. Without observations none of this would be possible.

Yet there are vast areas of the Arctic where there are few or no observations (e.g. Figure 2b), due to large uninhabited areas and distances, and to a challenging environment. A large region lacking almost any sustained observations across all the three main domains of the climate system (atmosphere, sea ice and ocean) is the Arctic Ocean. Satellites cannot see below the ocean surface and the very few *in-situ* profiling observations from the Central Arctic Ocean are usually from sporadic scientific summer expeditions. While satellites are efficient in separating sea ice from open ocean, they struggle with sea ice thickness (uncertain, only retrieved in winter); other relevant information on the sea-ice conditions are even more difficult. Again, most detailed observations come from occasional science expeditions. Weather stations (Figure 2b) are only on land and although there are surface pressure observations from buoys, there are rarely reliable temperature measurements. Except from occasional soundings during scientific expeditions some summers (e.g. Figure 2c), there is essentially no profiling of the atmosphere at all below ~3-4 km; satellite microwave channels closer to the surface are “contaminated” by unknown surface conditions and not used. Passive satellite sensors struggle to separate clouds from sea ice, especially in winter when the visual wavelengths cannot be used, while satellites with active sensors usually do not reach beyond ~82°N. A consequence is, for example, that no temperature observations are assimilated into any reanalysis below 3-4 km; neither in the atmosphere, nor in the ocean or from the surface.

Figure 3 Schematic of satellite-derived atmospheric temperature (a) in the mid-troposphere and (b) low troposphere, < 3-4 km (Linus Magnusson, European Centre for Medium-range Weather Forecasts).

Thinking about sustainable solutions

Even with the most optimistic technological development scenario it is unlikely that atmosphere and ocean profiling for the Central Arctic Ocean region can rely entirely on autonomous systems. Instead, while still hoping for new technology, we should consider what can be done with current technology and capability within existing systems while using the resources better.

Assimilation of data into modeling is central for weather forecasting since decades, building on often operationally-oriented, but base funded, R&D in national agencies, often with local or regional Arctic presence. The academic community, living under vulnerable funding conditions across all disciplines, carry a large portion of Arctic observing. An alliance between the climate and weather forecasting communities, building climate monitoring on coupled reanalysis and optimizing innovative observing around this, would serve both communities well. The three-level observing system, using WMO in vocabulary, facilitates this:

- a *comprehensive network* with coupled data assimilation optimized around Arctic satellite capabilities, supported by operational observing and observations of opportunity
- a *baseline observing network* that, for the Arctic Ocean region, builds on satellite observations in the atmosphere and autonomous under-ice systems in the ocean
- a *reference observing network* based on ship-borne scientific expeditions, preferably spread across all seasons

All of three levels are important and needs a concerted effort across the scientific and operational communities, in terms of both the work and funding. This will require:

- improved coupled data assimilation, allowing both better utility of existing remote sensing, improved satellite sensors and underwater technology allowing real-time use of autonomous under-ice profilers (e.g. using submarine cables)
- coordinated frequent ship-based research expeditions, all deploying atmospheric and oceanic profiling, and ice observations that, importantly, distribute data in near-real-time
- the increasing amounts of shipping operating in the Arctic performing at least a minimum of ocean, sea-ice and atmospheric observations, sharing data in near-real-time
- vessels above a certain size carry out some profiling measurement (e.g. UAV, VMP, soundings, surface-based remote sensing etc.) and transmit data in near-real-time

Conclusions

With improved collaboration, both internationally and also between the climate and weather forecasting communities, a sustainable observing system should be possible, building on current technologies and based on reanalysis optimized around satellite data and under-ice autonomous platforms, supported by high-quality measurements from frequent ship-borne science missions.